

Scientific Interpretation of Issues of Treatment, Communication in the Research of Psychologists of Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

This article includes the opinions of Uzbek psychologists about communication in their research. It was studied by them that priority is given to the issues of dialogue and communication in the development of a person, and a lot of information about the issues of dialogue and communication was presented.

Keywords: dialogue, treatment, communication, personality development, friendly attitude, rules of conduct, education, friendship.

INTRODUCTION. As you know, the issues of communication, treatment between people are relevant and important for each period. Communication, communication, exchange of information between people, communication occupy an important place, especially when entering into a relationship. It is worth noting that the treatment of people is formed on the basis of what factors make communication, and the study of what the mechanisms that influence them are, determines the relevance of the problem. In the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers, the issues of the formation and development of the personality take an important place in the issues of its education.

Issues of communication, treatment between people are relevant and important for each period. Communication, communication, exchange of information between people, communication occupy an important place, especially when entering into a relationship. It is worth noting that the treatment of people is formed on the basis of what factors make communication, and the study of what the mechanisms that influence them are, determines the relevance of the problem. In this regard, a number of research works have been carried out by scientists of the Republic, which serve to shed

light on one aspect of communication and treatment in human relations. priority is given by them to issues of treatment and communication in the maturation of the individual.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. V.Karimova [7] focuses on issues of treatment, communication in her research in the field of Social Psychology. According to him, we can see that on the basis of an analysis of the content of the concepts of communication, communication, treatment, he advanced his own author's position. Also, the socio-psychological factors of the development of communication in a person's personality, the sides of communication and the peculiarities of their manifestation in human activity are shown.

E.G'.Ghaziev [6] in his manual " the psychology of treatment " tried to focus on issues of treatment and communication. In the manual, the author focuses on the treatment that is the basis of human activity, revealing the psychological mechanisms of its manifestation along with the formation of a person. In particular, the development of R & D methods to determine the development of communicative skills in the individual, as well as the implementation of a wide range of scientific research in this area, laid the groundwork.

One of our scientists who has put forward a specific approach to his research on communication is P.S.Ergashev is [4]. In his methodological manual " the psychology of communication", he explained the content of the concepts of communication and communication, trying to substantiate the characteristic differences between them. In particular, within the framework of the manual, theoretical and empirical approaches to the content of the concept of communication, its functions and tasks, sides, age-related developmental features of communication have been put forward. It also provides methodological recommendations for psychodiagnostic methodologies and development, which serve to check the ability to communicate in an individual.

Discussion. In his research on social psychology, F.A.Akramova [1] touched on the issues of communication, communication, treatment, attitude and put forward her author's approach in this regard. At the same time, it should be noted that the introduction of an individual into social processes, communication plays an important role in his incarnation as an active member of society, and progress on the basis of age and activity are expressed with the help of reasonable thoughts. It is worth noting that when communication is directed to an individual, it is shown that it is effective, meaningful, it is associated with the satisfaction of their needs at a strong level in relation to information, information.

E.I.Ganeyeva's [12] research work on " the formation of the individual treatment style in adolescents in the educational process " focuses on studying the psychological mechanisms of individual treatment-formation as well as its role in the development of adolescent individuality. Also, within the framework of the research work, adolescents are studied in terms of the style of individual treatment in the structure of integral individuality, integral individuality taking into account the ethno-cultural factor and the place of individual style in its development. Also, in the educational process, the specifics of the formation of an individual style of treatment in students are explained. In particular, it has been shown that by organizing group work in the educational process, it is possible to develop one of the ways to increase the level of development of the style of individual treatment in adolescents. At the same time, the program for the formation of the developed method of individual treatment is based on the fact that it can be used by educators and psychologists in the process of working with high school teachers.

N. Sh.Mullaboyeva's [8] research work on " psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrection of the formation of feelings of loneliness in adolescents " investigated whether the formation of feelings of loneliness in adolescence is associated with such characteristics as lack of communication, low self-esteem, inability to adapt to a group. It has also been shown that a number of socio-psychological factors of feelings of loneliness in adolescents are associated with such personal characteristics as socio-adaptation, the formation of a positive attitude towards oneself associated with

communicative issues, the perception of one's own self-esteem, increasing communicative competence, a warm relationship with peers.

G.A.Kurbanova's [11] scientific research work on the "impact of interpersonal relationships in the family on child social perception" reveals that interpersonal relationships in the family influence the character of the child's communication process, depend on the feelings of sympathy or antipathy based on empirical research. In particular, the manifestation of the peculiarities of interpersonal relationships characteristic of adolescence, the psychological characteristics of social perception in adolescence and early adolescence are studied.

N.A.Gaibova's [5] scientific research work on "socio-psychological characteristics of relationships of adolescents of different sibling status with peers" investigated the socio-psychological characteristics of relationships of adolescents of different sibling status with peers using scientific research methods, as well as the influence of adolescent sibling status on group prestige.

RESULT. It should be noted that the relationship of adolescents with peers has its own socio-psychological characteristics, the circumstances characterizing the socio-psychological, sexual (gender) characteristics of the influence of a teenager's position in the family on the prestige of the group, including the fact that the eldest children take responsibility for overcoming a conflict situation more than other sibling status, younger children, on the other hand, have been found to be sociable towards their peers and have a high reputation in the group as well. It has also been shown that sibling relationships, a priority in the family environment, directly affect adolescents' relationships with their peers, the inability of single children, free from sibling relationships, to adapt to changes in socio-conditions causes problems in their relationships with peers.

N.T.Norkulova's research work on the topic "the motivation of affiliation – the socio-psychological factor that shapes the spiritual image of students" [9] focuses on the study of socio-psychological factors that influence the formation of the spiritual image of students by developing the motivation for affiliation. Especially as a factor in the formation of the spiritual image of students, the components of orientation towards affiliation and fear of rejection, the involvement of the affiliation motif with cognition, cognitive and integrative functions and self-assertion are revealed. Also, the socio-psychological characteristics of communication and treatment are indicated when striving for cooperation, entering into a relationship. Also, diagnostic methodologies of empirically researching the dependence of the attachment motif on social behavior and spirituality were developed as students. As a result, socio-psychological trainings and corporate trainings on the formation of the spiritual image of students were developed on the basis of the affiliation motive.

M.F. In the research work of Dadakhodjayeva [3] on the topic "psychological characteristics of the formation of treatment in college students", the characteristics of the formation of treatment in students of a vocational college and communicability are aimed at studying the specificity of the student. Within the framework of the study, treatment is considered one of the main forms of the psyche (along with activity, behavior), and treatment is manifested by its functional characteristics as a communicative systemic information transmission by the communicator, as a component of the educational process. It was also shown that the formation of a treatment rhythm is embodied in a complex composition as a system with a hierarchical structure, which is realized through certain stages, phases, levels, indicators, criteria. In particular, it has been established on the basis of empirical data that communicability is a factor in realizing the stability of an individual (student) in the manner of his or her ability to provide a process of treatment.

D.M.Anvarova's research work on "psychological characteristics of the formation and development of Adolescent spirituality" [2] reveals the content of measures aimed at researching the psychological mechanisms of the process of formation and development of adolescent spirituality and ensuring the effectiveness of this process. Also, within the framework of the research work, an author's program has been developed, in which a systematic approach to the process of formation

and development of adolescent spirituality, step-by-step goals and methods of its development are expressed.

N.D.Kasimova's research work [10] on the topic "the importance of sign socio-psychological characteristics in adolescent socialization" focuses on identifying the role, socio-psychological characteristics and forms of the Hebrew in adolescent socialization. Especially in adolescence, the formation of values into the process of socialization, norms in society, the assimilation of traditions as a result of taking an example from certain individuals, artistic representations was revealed on the basis of empirical research.

CONCLUSION. From the cited points, it can be seen that communication, in the studies of Uzbek psychologists, has been studied in a wide range. Accordingly, it provides the opportunity to formulate the following conclusions:

- the formation of communication in a person is characterized by their role in the system of social relations, the position they occupy;
- based on the research of scientists who scientifically studied the problems of adolescence, they are illuminated in terms of the formation of communication, socialization of the individual, the system of relations with peers, the rhythm of treatment, the motivation for affiliation.

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